

September 2021
Press Release

Accountability, Privacy and Resilience for Trustworthy AI driven cybersecurity in Europe

The consortium of **SPATIAL Project** (*Security and Privacy Accountable Technology Innovations, Algorithms, and Machine Learning*) announces the official start of this joint European initiative funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme.

Achieving trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a top priority for Europe.

Uncertainties in AI and opacity of data algorithms are demanding more efforts towards data privacy, resilience engineering, and legal-ethical accountability. This can be done by maximising the benefits of applying AI in numerous engineering and analytic solutions while preventing and minimising the risks. In critical domains such as cybersecurity, trustworthy AI can enhance security analytics and foster a more competitive offering of secure products and services.

SPATIAL will tackle the identified gaps on data and black-box AI by designing and developing resilient accountable metrics, privacy-preserving methods, verification tools and system solutions that will serve as critical building blocks for trustworthy AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity.

Besides the technical ambition, **SPATIAL will facilitate appropriate skill development and education for AI security** to strike a balance among technological complexity, societal complexity, and value conflicts in AI deployment.

The project covers data privacy, resilience engineering, and legal-ethical accountability, in line with Europe's priority to achieve trustworthy AI. The work carried out on both social and technical aspects will serve as a stepping stone to **establish an appropriate governance and regulatory framework for AI-driven security in Europe.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.

SPATIAL consortium is coordinated by Dr. Aaron Ding (TU Delft, Netherlands) and formed by 12 partners across 8 EU member states (Netherlands, Germany, Spain, Finland, France, Ireland, Serbia and Estonia). The consortium combines long-standing research expertise in AI, cybersecurity, IoT, edge computing, and lab-to-market know-how.

MORE INFO:

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